

ISic0241

I.Sicily inscription 0241

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]VSALL[---]

2. [---]OPATE[---]

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285275

EDR 127495

EDCS 10900669

Bibliography

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese.

Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica. Palermo / Rome. At 168

Ferrua, A 1941. *Analecta sicula. Epigraphica*. 3: 252-270. At 264 no.28b

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